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Utilization Of Available Instructional Technologies For Effective Academic Performance Of Business Education Students In Tertiary Institutions In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This research explored the level at which instructional technologies are utilized to enhance the academic performance of Business Education students in tertiary institutions across Delta State. The study was guided by five research questions and five corresponding hypotheses, which were developed based on the study's specific objectives and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. A broad range of relevant literature was examined to provide context and support for the study, along with a theoretical framework to interpret the findings. The theories employed include Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) and Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (1988), which underpin the study's rationale. The research adopted a survey design to collect data. The population consisted of 750 undergraduate Business Education students in Delta State, from which a sample of 150 was drawn using stratified random sampling based on academic levels. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire. The research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested with a t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Findings indicated that the use of available instructional technologies by Business Education students for improved academic performance was generally low. Additionally, the results showed no statistically significant differences in students' opinions on the instructional technologies needed for teaching business education based on their qualifications, among other variables. Based on these findings, the study recommended that tertiary institution stakeholders should allocate adequate funding to procure essential instructional technologies. Doing so would enhance both teaching and learning experiences, potentially leading to improved comprehension and academic outcomes for Business Education students.

Keywords: Business Education, students, instructional technologies

INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions are progressively adopting information and communication technology (ICT) tools and applications to enhance their programs and introduce greater flexibility into teaching and learning processes. Educational research covers a broad spectrum, examining how people learn about and engage with fields such as business, economics, and finance over time. It also explores how education can prepare individuals for modern challenges and adapt to the ever-changing requirements of the global economy. The integration of digital tools, such as online learning platforms and virtual classrooms,

enables students in business education programs to continue learning effectively within higher education institutions.

Business education is an academic field that seeks to equip students with the knowledge and skills necessary to thrive in the business world. Offered at multiple levels, including secondary and tertiary education, it provides students with both classroom instruction and practical experiences in real-world business contexts. Its focus is on teaching the principles and practices of the business environment, covering roles as consumers, producers, entrepreneurs, or employees. Students are instructed in business fundamentals, theories, and processes, with particular emphasis on subjects such as finance, accounting, marketing, management, human resources, organizational behavior, strategy, and economics. In addition to these core subjects, business education stresses the development of soft skills like leadership, communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking. These competencies are essential in the business world because they allow individuals to work effectively with others and navigate complex, technology-driven environments.

The study of business education is built upon a comprehensive understanding of the business practices, theories, and tools required to succeed in the competitive corporate world. This broad knowledge base forms the core of business education curricula. By combining classroom instruction with practical experience and the development of key skills, business education prepares students for a wide range of career opportunities and enables them to contribute positively to the business sector. Aliyu (as cited in Ojechi, 2015) defined business education as the acquisition and development of the skills, competencies, attitudes, and attributes necessary for the efficient functioning of a nation's economic system. Furthermore, business education plays a significant role in economic development by imparting knowledge and skills to learners. It also enables students to effectively share knowledge with others and to handle advanced office technologies and information systems during teaching practice exercises.

Business education is widely recognized as a key component in preparing young people for life and societal engagement (Osuala et al., 2018). Osuala et al. (2018) emphasize that its primary objective is to equip graduates with the skills needed for sustainable employment and societal advancement. Likewise, Umoeshiet (2015) describes business education as a field that prepares individuals for diverse roles in the business world by imparting essential knowledge and the pedagogical competencies needed to teach business concepts effectively. Akaeze (2014) similarly defines it as an integral part of the curriculum that equips learners with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes for success in the business world, noting that this curriculum develops practical competencies in areas such as clerical work, stenography, bookkeeping, accounting, data processing, marketing, sales, office administration, business ownership, and management. Furthermore, business education plays a pivotal role in fostering students' entrepreneurial development. In the current educational environment, business education students increasingly use devices such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops in their daily academic activities. However, the potential benefits of these technologies for improving academic performance remain largely unrealized. Consequently, integrating these technological tools into the instruction of business education courses has become essential to enhance learning outcomes.

In this context, the term instructional technologies refers to the tools, platforms, and methods used to facilitate learning and improve instructional practices. These technologies are designed to enhance educational delivery by making instruction more efficient, effective, and engaging. Hodges (2018) describes instructional technologies as tools and resources that facilitate learning and enhance the educational process, including hardware, software, and digital platforms used to deliver instructional content and support student learning. Over time, advances in instructional technologies have significantly transformed traditional teaching methods by providing educators with a wide array of resources to better support student learning.

Instructional technologies can be categorized in several ways. Internet-Based Training (IBT) is one form that uses the internet to deliver educational experiences. It has become increasingly prevalent due to widespread high-speed internet access and the need for flexible, scalable training solutions. IBT formats

include online courses, live webinars, virtual classrooms, and e-learning modules (Mayer, 2017). Another form is Computer-Based Training (CBT), which delivers education and training via computer technology. CBT can involve standalone software, web-based applications, or mobile platforms that often incorporate multimedia elements to facilitate learning (Moore, 2019).

Technology Enhanced Teaching (TET) is another category that involves integrating technology into educational practices to improve teaching and learning outcomes. This approach encompasses various tools, strategies, and methodologies that leverage digital technologies to transform traditional instruction (Clark, 2023). Additionally, digital technologies broadly include electronic tools, systems, and devices capable of generating, storing, or processing data. Digital technologies have revolutionized many aspects of society, from communication and education to healthcare and business (Connie, 2015), and their rapid advancement continues to produce innovative solutions that transform industries and everyday life. In the context of business education, the integration of technology into teaching and learning has significantly enhanced students' understanding of technology applications across various learning areas. Therefore, it is essential to empirically investigate how the use of available instructional technologies impacts student performance in business education programs at tertiary institutions in Delta State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The educational landscape has witnessed significant changes in recent years, largely driven by advancements in information and communication technology (ICT). Among these changes is the growing integration of instructional technologies in the delivery of business education programmes, offering new opportunities for innovation in teaching and learning.

However, despite these advancements, the effective use of instructional technology tools remains insufficient in many tertiary institutions. This gap is particularly evident in the business education field, where the expected application of modern instructional tools in classroom instruction is not consistently met. Compounding this issue is the concern expressed by employers about the apparent deficiency in performance-related competencies among graduates of business education programmes, particularly in their ability to effectively use instructional technologies within educational or business environments. As a result, many graduates are perceived as less competitive in both employment and entrepreneurial opportunities.

These concerns have motivated the current study, which seeks to examine how available instructional technologies are being utilized and to what extent their use influences the academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions across Delta State.

Given that business education is fundamentally linked to practical application and real-world teaching practices, it becomes imperative to bridge this gap. Investigating and addressing the underutilization of instructional technologies will help align the skills students acquire in school with the actual demands of the profession, thereby enhancing their readiness for the workforce and improving their overall academic success.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This research primarily aims to examine how extensively existing instructional technologies are utilized and how this usage affects the academic performance of business education students in Delta State's tertiary institutions. It will investigate the degree of use and potential benefits of these technologies in the educational process. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Identify the instructional technologies necessary for teaching business education in Delta State tertiary institutions.
2. Assess the extent to which available instructional technologies are utilized to enhance students' academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions.
3. Investigate the extent to which the use of available instructional technologies influences improvements in the academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

4. Examine the main constraints in using existing instructional technologies to improve the academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.
5. Ascertain the extent to which instructional technologies benefit the academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

1.4 Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. Which instructional technologies are required for teaching business education in Delta State tertiary institutions?
2. To what extent are the available instructional technologies being utilized to enhance students' academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent does the use of available instructional technologies impact the improvement of academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
4. What are the primary constraints in using existing instructional technologies to improve the academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
5. To what extent is the use of instructional technologies beneficial for improving the academic performance of business education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The study will test the following null hypotheses at the 0.05 significance level:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of business education students (based on their educational qualifications) regarding the instructional technologies required for teaching in Delta State tertiary institutions.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business education students concerning the extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective student academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of business education students (based on academic level) regarding the extent to which utilizing available instructional technologies impacts the improvement in academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of business education students (grouped by age) regarding the major constraints in using available instructional technologies to improve their academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions.
5. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of business education students (based on location) concerning the extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial for improving their academic performance in Delta State tertiary institutions.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study stands to benefit multiple stakeholders, including students, business education lecturers, curriculum developers, educational administrators, and future researchers. Upon completion, the research findings will be published in academic articles and journals to facilitate broader access and knowledge dissemination.

Primarily, the study will encourage both students and educators in the business education field to adopt and develop proficiency in instructional technologies, thereby enriching the teaching and learning processes. It will help to build capacity and practical competence in the use of digital tools, which are increasingly essential in modern educational environments.

Curriculum developers and education planners will also find the study valuable, as it will provide insights that could guide the inclusion of technology-centered strategies in business education curricula. This alignment with global digital trends will better prepare students with the relevant skills needed for career advancement and adaptability in an evolving job market.

Moreover, the study will contribute to more effective teaching and learning practices in business education programmes within Delta State tertiary institutions. The adoption of instructional technologies

can promote flexible learning opportunities, such as self-directed study and access to global educational content through online platforms, ultimately enhancing knowledge acquisition and instructional delivery. Administrators and programme managers in the institutions under study may also benefit from the improved student performance and instructional outcomes that effective use of technology brings. These benefits extend to better recruitment decisions, ensuring that personnel with relevant digital competencies are engaged.

Lastly, this research will serve as a useful reference for scholars and researchers interested in exploring the application of instructional technologies in business education. It will add to the existing body of knowledge and support further investigations into technology-integrated teaching methodologies.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study is specifically concerned with examining how the use of available instructional technologies affects the academic performance of students enrolled in business education programmes. It focuses on how these technologies are being utilized and the degree to which they contribute to effective learning outcomes.

The content scope includes the exploration of four categories of instructional technologies:

- Internet-Based Training (IBT)
- Computer-Based Training (CBT)
- Technology Enhanced Teaching (TET)
- Digital Technologies (DT)

Geographically, the study is limited to tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria, that offer business education programmes. These institutions include:

- Delta State University, Abraka
- University of Delta, Agbor
- College of Education, Warri
- Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba
- College of Physical Education, Mosogar

The findings from these institutions will form the basis for the study's conclusions and recommendations.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a survey research design, which was considered appropriate for gathering data from a large number of participants. The choice of this design was informed by the study's aim, to investigate how Business Education students in tertiary institutions across Delta State perceive the availability, usage, and effectiveness of instructional technologies in enhancing their academic performance.

The population for this study comprised 750 undergraduate students enrolled in Business Education programmes across five tertiary institutions in Delta State. These institutions included Delta State University, Abraka; University of Delta, Agbor; Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba; College of Physical Education, Mosogar; and College of Education, Warri. According to data obtained from the offices of the Heads of Departments, the student distribution was as follows: 185 from Delta State University, 92 from the University of Delta, 156 from the Federal College of Education (Technical), 178 from the College of Physical Education, and 139 from the College of Education, Warri.

Table 3.1: Population Distribution of Business Education Students from Tertiary Institutions in Delta State

Delta State University, Abraka	University of Delta, Agbor	Federal College of Education (Technical), Asaba	College of Physical Education, Mosogar	College of Education, Warri	Total
185	92	156	178	139	750

Source: Offices of Heads of Departments

To obtain a representative sample from this population, the stratified random sampling technique was employed. This involved dividing the students into subgroups based on their academic levels and selecting participants randomly from each subgroup. A total of 150 students, representing 20% of the population, were sampled. The selection ensured an even distribution across academic levels, with 30 students drawn randomly from each group, namely, 400-level, 200-level, and NCE I and II students, across the five institutions.

Table 3.2: Sample Size of Business Education Students from Tertiary Institutions in Delta State

Delta State University, Abraka	University of Delta, Agbor	Federal College of Education, Asaba	College of Physical Education, Mosogar	College of Education, Warri	Sample size
400 Level Students	200 Level Students	NCE I11 Students	NCE I Students	NCE II Students	
30	30	30	30	30	150

Data were collected using a researcher-designed questionnaire titled *Extent of Utilization of Instructional Technologies Questionnaire (EOUOITQ)*. The instrument consisted of two parts. Section A gathered demographic data, while Section B addressed the core research questions using a 4-point Likert-type scale. The response options included Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). Participants were asked to select the option that best represented their views.

To ensure the instrument measured what it was intended to, it underwent face and content validation by three experts. Two reviewers were from the Department of Business Education and one from the Department of Guidance and Counselling, all at Delta State University, Abraka. These experts evaluated the questionnaire for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. Their feedback was incorporated to enhance the instrument’s precision and eliminate ambiguity.

The reliability of the questionnaire was established through a pilot study using the test-retest method. Thirty Business Education students from the University of Benin, outside the scope of the main study, completed the instrument on two occasions spaced two weeks apart. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was used to analyze the consistency of responses, resulting in a reliability coefficient of 0.84, which indicates that the instrument was highly reliable.

For efficient data collection, the researcher enlisted the help of five research assistants, one from each participating institution. These assistants were trained on the purpose of the study and the proper administration of the questionnaire. They were also guided on how to resolve participant queries and ensure that the responses were complete and accurately recorded.

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The research questions were addressed using mean scores and standard deviation, while t-tests and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were applied to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Interpretations of mean scores followed a structured scale: scores below 1.50 indicated Very Low Extent or Strong Disagreement; 1.50 to 2.49 indicated Low Extent or Disagreement; 2.50 to 3.49 reflected High Extent or Agreement; and scores from 3.50 upward represented Very High Extent or Strong Agreement. In hypothesis testing, a p-value less than 0.05 resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis, while a p-value greater than 0.05 led to its acceptance.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The findings of the study are tabulated as follows:

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business education students on instructional technologies required in teaching business education students

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	REMARK
What are the instructional technologies required in teaching business education students in your institution?				
1.	Typing (Mavis Beacon, Ultra key)	2.86	0.72	Agree
2.	Power Point for Lecture Presentation	2.77	0.68	Agree
3	Interactive Websites	3.02	0.79	Agree
4	Online Tutorial in Zoom	2.72	0.85	Agree
5	Statistical Analysis and Forecasting	2.59	0.75	Agree
6	Internet Browsing	2.76	0.87	Agree
7	Intranet/Extranet	2.69	0.88	Agree
8	Learning Management System (LMS)	2.55	0.74	Agree
9	Virtual Reality (VR) Simulation	2.68	0.81	Agree
10	Video Conferencing (e.g., Skype, Microsoft Teams)	2.57	0.79	Agree
11	Online Assessment and Testing	2.85	0.70	Agree
12	Collaborative Document Editing Tools (e.g., Google Docs)	2.51	0.95	Agree
Grand Mean/SD		2.71	0.79	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.1 shows the mean responses on instructional technologies required in teaching business education students. The mean rating ranges from 2.51 to 3.02. Hence, all the items mean responses agree that the items listed on the table above as instructional technologies are required in teaching business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. While the standard deviation ranges from 0.68 to 0.95, with a grand standard deviation of 0.79 shows that the respondents were very close in their responses.

Table 4.2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business education students on extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective students' academic performance

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	REMAR
What is the extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective students' academic performance in your institution?				
13.	Typing (Mavis Beacon, Ultra key)	2.97	0.83	HE
14.	PowerPoint for Lecture Presentation	2.75	0.87	HE
15.	Interactive Websites	1.54	0.87	LE
16.	Online Tutorial in Zoom	2.17	0.84	LE
17.	Statistical Analysis and Forecasting	2.30	0.68	LE
18.	Internet Browsing Software	2.53	0.93	HE
19.	Intranet/Extranet	1.85	0.79	LE

20.	Learning Management System (LMS)	2.47	0.81	LE
21.	Virtual Reality (VR) Simulation	2.45	0.94	LE
22.	Video Conferencing (e.g., Skype, Microsoft Teams)	2.41	0.91	LE
23.	Online Assessment and Testing	2.40	0.97	LE
24.	Collaborative Document Editing Tools (e.g., Google Docs)	2.46	0.95	LE
Grand Mean/SD		2.36	0.87	LE

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.2 shows the mean responses on extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective students' academic performance. The mean range from 1.54 to 2.97. The table discloses three items with mean that corresponds to high extent of utilization, while nine items have means that correspond to low level of utilization. However, the grand mean of 2.36 indicates a low extent of utilization of the available instructional technologies for effective students' academic performance. While the standard deviation ranges from 0.68 to 0.97, with a grand standard deviation of 0.87. This indicates that the respondents were very close in their responses.

Table 4.3: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business education students on the extent to which the utilization of instructional technologies has an impact on improving students' academic performance

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	REMARK
To what extent does the utilization of available instructional technologies have an impact on improving business education students' academic performance in your institution?				
25.	Typing (Mavis Beacon, Ultra key)	2.90	0.50	HE
26.	Power Point for Lecture Presentation	2.85	0.69	HE
27.	Interactive Websites	2.41	0.81	LE
28.	Motion Films	2.07	0.82	LE
29.	Statistical Analysis and Forecasting Software	2.26	0.81	LE
30.	Internet Browsing	2.62	0.83	HE
31.	Search Engine (e.g. Google.com, firefox.com)	2.72	0.84	HE
32.	Spread Sheet (Excel)	2.13	0.77	LE
33.	Virtual Reality (VR) Simulation	2.01	0.60	LE
34.	Collaborative Document Editing Tools (e.g., Google Docs)	2.16	0.69	LE
35.	Online Assessment and Testing	2.27	0.71	LE
36.	Video Conferencing (e.g., Skype, Microsoft Teams)	2.17	0.87	LE
37.	Learning Management System (LMS)	2.31	0.78	LE
Grand Mean/SD		2.38	0.75	LE

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.3 shows the mean responses on the extent to which the utilization of instructional technologies has an impact on improving students' academic performance. The mean ranges from 2.01 to 2.90. The table reveals four items with means that correspond to a high extent to which the utilization of instructional technologies has an impact on improving students' academic performance, while nine of the items have means that correspond to a low extent. However, the grand mean of 2.38 shows a low extent to which the utilization of instructional technologies has an impact on improving students' academic

performance. While the standard deviation ranges from 0.50 to 0.87, with a grand standard deviation of 0.75. This shows that the respondents were close in their responses to the mean.

Table 4.4: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business education students on major constraints in using available instructional technologies

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	REMARK
	What are the major constraints in using available instructional technologies to improve academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State?			
38.	Insufficient funding for instructional technologies implementation and maintenance.	2.74	0.99	Agree
39.	Limited technical support for instructional technologies platforms.	2.59	0.98	Agree
40.	Inadequate internet connectivity for effective instructional technologies	2.75	0.96	Agree
41.	Resistance from faculty members towards adopting instructional technologies methods	2.65	0.97	Agree
42.	Lack of training and professional development opportunities for faculty members on instructional technologies	2.54	0.97	Agree
43.	Limited awareness and understanding of instructional technologies benefits	2.89	0.83	Agree
44.	Inadequate infrastructure and facilities for instructional technologies	2.81	0.82	Agree
45.	Scarcity of high-quality instructional technologies content and resources	2.91	0.79	Agree
46.	Concerns about data security and privacy on instructional technologies platforms	2.30	0.80	Disagree
47.	Regulatory or policy constraints affecting instructional technologies implementation	2.44	0.94	Disagree
48.	Lack of integration with existing educational technologies and systems.	2.36	0.84	Disagree
49.	Incompatibility with existing curriculum and teaching methods.	2.43	0.93	Disagree
50.	Insufficient technical skills among students and faculty members for instructional technologies.	3.15	0.87	Agree
51.	High cost of instructional technologies and resources.	2.61	0.89	Agree
52.	Difficulty in monitoring and assessing student progress in instructional technologies environments.	2.97	0.76	Agree
	Grand Mean/SD	2.68	0.89	Agree

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.4 reveals the mean responses on the major constraints in using available instructional technologies to improve the academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions. The mean rating ranges from 2.30 to 3.15, while eleven items in the scale have mean responses that agree that the items listed are major constraints in using available instructional technologies to improve the academic performance of business education students, while four of the items disagree that they are not

major constraints. However, the grand mean of 2.68 displays that there are major constraints in using available instructional technologies in improving business education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State. While the standard deviation ranges from 0.76 to 0.99 with a grand standard deviation

Table 4.5: Mean and Standard Deviation responses of business education students on extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial on improving academic performance of business education students

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	X	SD	REMARK
Extent to which the use of instructional technologies are beneficial on improving academic performance of business education students in your institution.				
53.	Using computers for lectures	2.99	0.88	HE
54.	Computer-based laboratory	3.53	0.66	VHE
55.	Using power point presentations in business education lectures	2.51	0.99	HE
56.	Using graphics to make explanations clearer	2.92	0.96	HE
57.	Linking students and teachers with online libraries	2.78	0.93	HE
58.	Using computer simulation in teaching business education courses	2.35	0.74	LE
59.	Video/teleconferencing for teaching learning and research activities	2.83	0.89	HE
60.	Use of CD-ROMs and DVDs for storing prepared lectures/containing prepares business education lectures	3.14	0.88	HE
61.	Computer-assisted instructional packages	2.23	0.73	LE
62.	Constant use of Online lectures/tutorial	2.17	0.90	LE
63.	Interactive whiteboards for real-time collaboration	2.01	0.85	LE
64.	Online discussion forums for student engagement	2.98	0.94	HE
65.	Gamification of learning activities for increased motivation.	1.65	0.72	LE
66.	Mobile learning apps for flexible learning opportunities	2.75	0.93	LE
67.	Virtual reality experiences for immersive learning environments	3.60	0.58	VHE
Grand Mean/SD		2.70	0.84	HE

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Table 4.5 shows the mean responses on the extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial in improving the academic performance of business education students. The mean ranges from 1.65 to 3.60. The table indicates two items with a mean that corresponds to a very high extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial in improving the academic performance of business education students. Also, seven of the items have a mean that corresponds to a high extent, while six of the items have means that correspond to a low extent. However, the grand mean of 2.70 reveals a high extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial on improving the academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. While the standard deviation ranges from 0.58 to 0.99, with a grand standard deviation of 0.84. This shows that the respondents were very close in their responses.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings on research question one reveals that instructional technologies such as Mavis Beacon, Ultra key, Power Point, interactive Websites, Online Tutorial in Zoom, Statistical Analysis and Forecasting,

Internet Browsing, Intranet/Extranet, Learning Management System (LMS), Virtual Reality (VR) Simulation, Video Conferencing (e.g., Skype, Microsoft Teams), Online Assessment and Testing and Collaborative Document Editing Tools (e.g., Google Docs) are required in teaching business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This findings corroborate that of Chukwu-Umahi and Okoli (2023) who found that basic instructional technology tools such as email and instant messaging were frequently used, more sophisticated tools like blogs, collaborative authoring platforms, and social networking were underutilized.

The findings of research question two shows a low extent of utilization of the available instructional technologies for effective business education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State. The finding support Eze and Osuji (2022), who upheld that instructional technologies are widely available but not fully utilized in many Business Education programs. Equally, the finding harmonizes that of Owolabi and Oyewole (2020) that while instructional technologies like projectors, computers, and e-learning platforms were available in some institutions, their use was inconsistent and often limited. This finding contradicts the finding of Ademiluyi et al. (2023) who found that skills acquisition resources are available for teaching and learning and that the available skills acquisition resources in business education are utilized in teaching and learning of business education to a high extent. This is also in agreement with Baba et al. (2022) who discovered that OTM lecturers made use of google classroom, blackboard, flop, Ednidi, presi to a low extent

Further, the findings of research question three demonstrates that there is a low extent to which utilization of instructional technologies have impact on improving business education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This could be as a result of the low extent of utilization of available instruction technologies in these tertiary institutions in the state. This findings agrees with that of Adegoke (2019); Mishra et al., (2022) who found in their studies that without ongoing training, there is a risk that educators may not fully utilize the capabilities of instructional technologies, thereby limiting their impact on students learning.

Similarly, the findings of research question four displays that there are major constraints in using available instructional technologies such as such as Insufficient funding for instructional technologies implementation and maintenance, Limited technical support for instructional technologies platforms; Inadequate internet connectivity for effective instructional technologies; Resistance from faculty members towards adopting instructional technologies methods; Lack of training and professional development opportunities for faculty members on instructional technologies; Limited awareness and understanding of instructional technologies benefits, Inadequate infrastructure and facilities for instructional technologies; Scarcity of high-quality instructional technologies content and resources in using available instructional technologies; Insufficient technical skills among students and faculty members for instructional technologies; High cost of instructional technologies and resources and Difficulty in monitoring and assessing student progress in instructional technologies environments to improve academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This findings is in agreement with Chukwu-Umahi and Okoli (2023) who found that challenges such as lack of infrastructure, poor internet connectivity, and insufficient administrative support, greatly limited the effective use of instructional technologies in education. Further, the finding corroborate that of Adeoye and Bello (2019), who found that one of the major challenges in utilizing instructional technologies in Business Education is the lack of infrastructure. Poor internet connectivity, lack of sufficient computers, and limited access to digital learning materials. Again, the study's finding is in consonant with that of Selwyn and Facer (2021) who found in their study that Face-to-face interactions, networking, and the ability to read non-verbal cues are essential in business but may be underemphasized in heavily technology-mediated environments

The finding on research question five reveals a high extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial on improving academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State. This findings is in line with Topi et al., (2021) who discovers that the integration of instructional technologies in business education equips students with essential digital literacy and

technological skills that assist students to develop the competencies required in the modern workplace. This finding also support Sharma et al. (2023) who found that practical application of technology prepares students for roles that require strong analytical skills. The finding agree with Bower (2020) who discovered that instructional technology tools mimic the collaborative nature of the modern business environment, helping students develop teamwork and communication skills that are essential in business settings. Also, the finding is in harmony with Adegoke (2019) that where ICT has been effectively integrated, there are clear improvements in student engagement, understanding of complex concepts, and practical skills development.

The result of hypothesis one indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of business education students on instructional technologies required in teaching business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State on the basis of educational qualification in view.

The findings on hypothesis two reveals that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on gender. This is in line with Bukoye (2018) who found no significant difference between male and female students respondents towards availability of enough and relevant materials for teachers used in both private and government owned schools. Also, the result is in line with Nnajofofor and Ejikeme (2020) who proved that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of business studies teachers on the extent of utilization of multimedia projectors and interactive whiteboard based on gender.

The findings on hypothesis three show that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on the extent to which the utilization of available instructional technologies has an impact on improving business education students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Delta State, based on academic level.

Findings on hypothesis four indicate that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on major constraints in using available instructional technologies to improve the academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State based on age. This finding is in agreement with Nnajofofor and Ejikeme (2020), who found that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of business studies teachers on the extent of utilization of multimedia projectors and interactive whiteboards on the basis of age.

Findings on hypothesis five display that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of business education students on the extent to which the use of instructional technologies is beneficial in improving the academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State, based on location.

CONCLUSION

Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that extent of utilization of available instructional technologies for effective academic performance of business education students in tertiary institutions in Delta State is low. The study also concluded that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of business education students on extent to which the utilization of available instructional technologies have impact on improving business education students' academic performance in tertiary institution in Delta State based on academic level.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Stakeholders of tertiary institutions should ensure that they provide the necessary funds require for the purchase of the required instructional technologies for the teaching and learning of business education as these instructional technologies might help to improve the understanding of the students, hence, it might equally help to effectively improve their academic performance in their various institutions.

2. Lecturers and business education students in the various tertiary institutions should ensure that they utilize the available instructional technologies provided for their use. As this might go a long way to effectively improve the students' academic performance since they can see, feel and make use of these instructional technologies.
3. The school management should ensure that lecturers are trained and retrained through workshops, seminars and conferences on how to effectively make use of these instructional technologies. As this might encourage them to make adequate use of the available instructional technologies in their possession during the process of teaching and learning of business education.
4. A study of this nature should be recreated in other geographical location for improved and better result.

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